

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF RC-BEAMS STRENGTHENED IN SHEAR WITH U-WRAP CFRP FABRICS

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ABSTRACT

The development of finite element (FE) software and comprehensive constitutive laws made the simulation of externally bonded reinforced concrete (EB-RC) beams strengthened in shear with FRP reliable and cost-effective. The objective of the present study is to evaluate the experimental results of nine EB-RC T-beam specimens strengthened in shear with carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) by modelling them using FE software and considering the variation of strain, load, and deflection in each component of those beams, particularly, the interaction of those components during the process of loading until failure. These features give an insightful understanding of behaviour of such specimens.

KEYWORDS

Reinforced concrete beams; finite element modelling; carbon fiber reinforced polymer wrap; size effect; shear strengthening; effective strain

INTRODUCTION

Externally bonded fiber reinforced polymers (EB-FRP) are applied for strengthening damaged reinforced concrete (RC) elements due to their high strength-to weight ratio, simple installations, high strength in low temperature. One of the common deficiencies in RC components is the shear failures in RC beams that can be rehabilitated by EB-FRP materials. Also, because of the numerous applications of them in shear strengthening, the guidelines have proposed different equations for estimation of their shear contributions in damaged RC beams in shear (D'Antino & Triantafillou, 2016; Kotynia et al., 2021; Mohammadi et al., 2023). As it is presented in Figure 1, not considering the size effects result in overestimating the shear contribution of EB-FRP (Benzeguir et al., 2017). By developing numerical techniques, they have become decent substitutes for laboratory tests, as they have shown high accuracy in predicting the responses of such beams, less time-consuming, and cost-effectiveness. The aim of the current study is to validate the accuracy of the finite elements analysis (FEA) to those of the experimental tests through simulating nine RC beams without steel-stirrups strengthened in shear with EB-CFRP by emphasizing the size effect on both shear contributions of the EB-CFRP and the concrete. The specimens are adopted from research conducted by Benzeguir et al. (2019). The beams are classified into three categories which are small, medium, and large specimens. In each category, one beam is considered as a control beam and not strengthened with EB-CFRP, another beam is strengthened with one layer of CFRP wrap, and a third beam is strengthened with two layers of CFRP wrap. The results are presented in terms of load-deflection responses, shear crack patterns, failure modes, and strains distribution along the main shear cracks.

Figure 1: Calculated ACI 440.2R 2017 code versus laboratory tests

EXPERIMENTAL MODEL

The simulated models are adopted from the research conducted by Benzeguir et al. (2019) which are nine beams strengthened with EB-CFRP in different sizes as they are presented in Figure 2. The concrete compression strength is $f'_c = 30 \text{ MPa}$ for all the specimens. The details of the specimens with different sizes are presented in Figure 2. The distances between the supports (L_m) for the small, medium and, large specimens are 1580 mm, 3110 mm, and 4430 mm, respectively, and the shear spans of those beams are $a = 3d$. The CFRP composites have an elastic modulus of 231 GPa, a tensile strength of 3650 MPa, and a tensile elongation of 1.4%.

Figure 2: a) Elevation of beams b) Cross-sections of beams

SIMULATED MODEL

Concrete under tensile and shear stress (cracked concrete)

There are different types of concrete materials in ABAQUS library, such as the concrete damage plasticity (CDP), the brittle cracking (BC), and smeared crack model. However, CDP model is selected to simulate the behaviour of the concrete in tension and compression. The rotated smeared crack model is implemented in the framework of the concrete damage plasticity. The drawback of the smeared crack modelling is the strain localization when the element size reduces, resulting in zero energy loss in the tension-softening curve of concrete (Chen et al., 2012). In order to avoid this phenomenon, the crack band model is defined in CDP model to solve the divergence challenge in the analysis Bažant & Becq-Giraudon (2002). The rotating smeared crack model transforms the cracking strain to the cracking displacement (crack width) as follows:

$$w = \int_h \varepsilon_{cr} dh \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where ε_{cr} is the cracking strain, and h is the crack band width as it is presented in Figure 3, which is equal to $h = \sqrt{2}L$ where L is the length of the square element.

Figure 3: Crack band width for four nodes element

For defining the response of the concrete in tension (Tension-softening curve), the equation introduced by Hordijk (1991) is applied for the simulations as follows:

$$\frac{\sigma}{f_t} = \left[1 + \left(c_1 \frac{w}{w_{cr}} \right)^3 \right] e^{-c_2 \frac{w}{w_{cr}}} - \frac{w}{w_{cr}} (1 + c_1^3) e^{-c_2} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$w_{cr} = 5.14 \frac{G_f}{f_t} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$f_t = 1.4 \left(\frac{f'_c - 8}{10} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$G_f = (0.0469 d_a^2 - 0.5 d_a + 26) \left(\frac{f'_c}{10} \right)^{0.7} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

The shear retention factor is adopted from the model proposed by Rots (1988) as follows, and the tension-softening curve is presented in Figure 4.

$$\beta = \left(1 - \frac{\varepsilon_{11}^{cr}}{\varepsilon_u} \right)^p \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

Figure 4: Tension softening curve for $f'_c = 30 \text{ MPa}$

Concrete behaviour under compression

The compression behaviour of the concrete is adopted from the model introduced by Saenz (1964) and it is presented in Equation 7 and Figure 5.

Figure 5: Compression behaviour of concrete for $f'_c = 30 \text{ Mpa}$

$$\sigma_c = \frac{\alpha \varepsilon}{1 + [(\alpha \varepsilon_p / \sigma_p) - 2](\varepsilon / \varepsilon_p) + (\varepsilon / \varepsilon_p)^2} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

Bond-slip model between concrete and EB-CFRP

Definition of the interface layer between concrete and CFRP wraps has a significant impact on the shear contribution of CFRP wraps and the ultimate load-carrying capacities of strengthened RC beams. In fact, considering perfect bond model (formerly implemented in FE analysis) leads to an inaccurate analysis of the above-mentioned beams in three different ways: 1) the overestimation of ultimate load-carrying capacities; 2) wrong distribution of the main and marginal shear cracks; 3) wrong conception of failure modes at the interface layers. Therefore, in the current research, the bond-slip models introduced by Lu et al. (2005) is assigned to the cohesive layers as shown in Figure 6 and the following equations. For defining the behaviour of interface layer, the cohesive element is selected to simulate the bond behaviour between concrete and EB-CFRP.

$$\tau = \tau_{max} \sqrt{\frac{s}{s_0}} \quad \text{if } s \leq s_0 \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$\tau = \tau_{max} e^{-\alpha \left(\frac{s}{s_0} - 1\right)} \quad \text{if } s > s_0 \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

Figure 6: Bond-slip model between concrete and CFRP wrap for $f'_c = 30 \text{ Mpa}$ proposed by Lu et al. (2005)

Schematic of Simulated model in ABAQUS

In order to verify the result of the simulation, the properties of materials used in experimental tests conducted by Benzeguir et al. (2019) are implemented in this study. In addition, the schematic of simulated models and their discretization in ABAQUS regarding the components of strengthened RC beams are presented in Figure 7 (a to g). The beams are subjected to three-point loadings (shear span $a = 3d$), as shown in Figure 7-b. the interaction between longitudinal bars and concrete is assigned from the model introduced by Telford (1993) as cohesive layers (Figure 7-a). The interaction between EB-CFRPs and concrete is implemented from the model proposed by Lu et al. (2005) as interface layers (Figure 7-f). The material properties of the concrete reported in these experimental investigations are used as the input parameters in ABAQUS. The RC beam strengthened in shear with EB-CFRP wrap has identical properties of the beam that is subjected to experimental tests.

VERIFICATION WITH LABORATORY RESULTS

Pattern of shear cracks and load-displacement responses

The results obtained from the FEA are compared with the experimental tests for the control (not strengthened with EB-CFRPs wrap) small, medium, and large beams in terms of crack patterns and load-deflection responses in order to validate the numerical models. The studies conducted by (Chaallal et al., 2002; Chen et al., 2012; Pellegrino & Modena, 2002) proved that a single shear crack occurs in specimens not strengthened in shear with internal steel-stirrups. Indeed, in all control beams, the numerical FEA shows single shear cracks as the dominant failure mode, identical to that obtained from the experimental tests, which shows that the proposed numerical model is able to accurately predict the shear crack pattern and failure modes (Figure 8).

Figure 7: Simulated RC-T beam strengthened in shear with EB-CFRP wrap a) interaction between longitudinal bars and concrete b) Schematic of the simulated experimental beam c) Schematic of the simulated steel reinforcements d) transverse steel discretization e) CFRP-wrap discretization f) interaction between EB-CFRP and concrete g) concrete discretization

Figure 8: Shear crack patterns at the ultimate states for the control beams
a) small control beam b) medium control beam c) large control beam

The load-deflection responses of control beams are presented in Figure 9. As shown for all the specimens, the same trend of curves has been obtained from the FEA and the experimental tests, confirming the validity and assumptions applied to the simulated model.

Figure 9: Load-deflection responses of the control specimens (experimental results versus FEA)

The predicted maximum load and displacement obtained from the numerical analysis and the experimental testing results are presented in Table 1. For the small control beam, the maximum load and the corresponding displacement obtained from the FEA are 62.2 kN and 1.9 mm, which are 9.3% and 5.5% higher than those of the experimental results, respectively. For the medium control beam, the values obtained are 127.1 kN and 2.7 mm, 3.8% and 3.5% higher than the laboratory tests. For the large control beam, the maximum load and the corresponding displacement reported from FEA are 295.2 kN and 4 mm, 4.3% and 2.5% higher than those of the experimental tests. Therefore, for all control beams, the difference between the FEA and the experimental results ranged between 2.5 and 9.3% (less than 10%), confirming the accuracy of the proposed numerical model.

Table 1: Load-displacement responses of control beams (FEA vs. experimental tests)

Experimental results		Numerical results		Displacement ratio NUM/EXP	Load ratio NUM/EXP
Small control beam				1.055	1.093
Displacement (mm)	Load (kN)	Displacement (mm)	Load (kN)		
1.8	56.9	1.9	62.2		
Medium control beam				1.038	1.035
2.6	122.7	2.7	127.1		
Large control beam				1.025	1.043
3.9	282.9	4	295.2		

EFFECTIVE STRAINS IN THE SPECIMENS STRENGTHENED WITH EB-CFRP WRAPS

The effective strains ($\varepsilon_{f,e}$) are calculated by multiplying the distribution factors (D_{FRP}) to maximum strains (ε_{max}) experienced by the fibers as follows (Chen, 2010):

$$D_{FRP} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \varepsilon_{FRP,i}}{n\varepsilon_{max}} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

The strain profiles along the normalized main shear cracks for all the six strengthened specimens are presented in Figure 10, and by taking advantage of the FEA, the distribution factors and corresponding effective strains are calculated and compared to the existing guidelines. Table 2 presents the maximum CFRP strains obtained from the FEA. It can be observed that by increasing the size of the strengthened specimens with one EB-CFRP layer from small (specimen S0-1L) to medium (M0-1L) and then to large (L0-1L) beams, the maximum strains decreased from 6372 $\mu\varepsilon$, to 3983 $\mu\varepsilon$, and then to 3473 $\mu\varepsilon$, respectively. Similarly, for the strengthened specimens with two layers of EB-CFRP wraps, the maximum strains decreased from 4932 $\mu\varepsilon$ to 3129 $\mu\varepsilon$, and then to 1420 $\mu\varepsilon$ for specimens S0-2L, M0-2L, and L0-2L, respectively. In addition, the results show that the maximum strains decreased by increasing the number of CFRP layers.

The effective CFRP strains obtained from the FEA are based on the model proposed by Chen & Teng (2003-a), Chen & Teng (2003-b), and Chen (2010), as follows:

$$V_f = 2f_{f,e}t_f w_f \frac{h_{f,e}(\cot\theta + \cot\beta) \sin\beta}{s_f} \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

$$f_{f,e} = E_f \varepsilon_{f,e} = E_f \varepsilon_{max} D_{FRP} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

The EB-CFRP effective strains of specimens with different sizes and rigidities obtained from FEA are compared with the predicted EB-CFRP effective strains from ACI 440.2R-17 design guideline. Table 2 presents the effective strains obtained from the FEA compared to those of the ACI 440.2R-17. For the small beams, the effective strains obtained from the FEA are 4870 $\mu\varepsilon$ and 3686 $\mu\varepsilon$ for S0-1L and S0-2L, respectively, which are 132% and 38% higher than the effective strains predicted by the ACI 440.2R-17 (2159 $\mu\varepsilon$ and 2701 $\mu\varepsilon$), proving that the ACI 440.2R-17 underestimates the effective strains in beams with small sizes. However, for the medium beams, the effective strains obtained from the numerical FEA are lower than those of the guideline (2982 $\mu\varepsilon$ and 2501 $\mu\varepsilon$ for M0-1L and M0-2L, respectively, compared to 4365 $\mu\varepsilon$ and 3270 $\mu\varepsilon$ from the ACI guideline). Likewise, for the large beams, the effective CFRP strains obtained from the FEA are lower than those of the guideline (2639 $\mu\varepsilon$ and 1120 $\mu\varepsilon$ for L0-1L and L0-2L, respectively, compared to 3970 $\mu\varepsilon$ and 2811 $\mu\varepsilon$ predicted by the guideline). Therefore, the ACI 440.2R overestimates the effective strains for medium and large strengthened RC beams. Furthermore, increasing the rigidity of EB-CFRP wraps (by increasing the number of CFRP layers) leads to reductions in the effective strains for all sizes of strengthened RC beams. However, for small beams, the guideline shows an increase in the effective strains when increasing the EB-CFRP rigidity (Table 2).

Figure 10: Maximum strain on fibers intercepted by major shear cracks

Table 2: Comparisons between effective strain (FEA versus ACI 440.2R 2017)

Specimens	Maximum strains (µε)	Distribution factors	Effective strains (µε) (FEA)	Effective strains (µε) (ACI 440.2R 2017)	Effective strains ratio NUM/ACI 440.2R 2017
S0-1L	6372	0.764	4870	2159	2.25
S0-2L	4932	0.747	3686	2701	1.36
M0-1L	3983	0.749	2982	4365	0.68
M0-2L	3129	0.799	2501	3270	0.76
L0-1L	3473	0.760	2639	3970	0.66
L0-2L	1420	0.789	1120	2811	0.40

CONCLUSIONS

This research deals with the numerical modelling of RC beam strengthened in shear with EB-CFRP wraps in order to evaluate the accuracy of FEA results to those of the experimental tests. Followings are the conclusions drawn from this study:

- The proposed numerical model is able to predict the experimental results with high accuracy, and the results obtained from the FEA can be extracted in various ways, allowing a more comprehensive data analysis than experimental tests of RC beams shear strengthened with EB-CFRP wraps.
- The size effect is a fundamental factor for predicting the EB-CFRP effective strains and should be considered in current design guidelines. In fact, significant differences in the effective strains are obtained between the FEA and the ACI 440.2R predictions. Also, by increasing the size of beams from small to medium and large, the effective strains decrease in the FEA and experimental results, while they increase according to the ACI guideline.
- Increasing the CFRP rigidity by increasing the number of EB-CFRP layers, in all strengthened beams (small, medium, and large sizes), leads to reductions in the effective strains, except for the guideline prediction for small beams where an increase in effective strains occurs.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The financial support of the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC) and the Fonds de recherche du Québec–Nature et technologie (FRQNT) through operating grants is gratefully acknowledged.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

Concrete

c_1, c_2 = constant parameters obtained from tensile tests of concrete

w_{cr} = crack width at zero stress

w = crack width

σ = tensile stress in normal direction of crack

f_t = tensile stress normal to the crack direction

θ = shear crack angle

G_f = fracture energy

f_t = maximum tensile stress of concrete

S_f = space between FRP strips

d_a = biggest aggregate dimension

f'_c = compressive concrete strength

β = shear retention factor in concrete

ε_{11}^{cr} = principal tensile cracking strain

ε_u^{cr} = ultimate strain corresponding to zero stress normal to crack

P = ratio of shear degradation

σ_c = applied concrete stress

α = concrete elasticity modulus

ε = compressive strain corresponding to applied compressive stress in concrete

ε_p = compressive strain corresponding to maximum compressive stress in concrete

σ_p = maximum compressive cylindrical strength in concrete (f'_c)

Bond-slip between EB-CFRP and concrete

τ = shear stress on interface layer between concrete and EB – CFRP

τ_{max} = maximum shear stress on interface layer between concrete and EB – CFRP

s = slip corresponding to shear stress on bond – slip between concrete and EB – CFRP

s_0 = slip corresponding to maximum shear stress on bond – slip between concrete and CFRP

α = coefficients in proposed bond– slip models

Properties of FRP

V_f = shear contribution of FRP

E_f = FRP elasticity modulus

$f_{f,e}$ = effective stress

$\varepsilon_{f,e}$ = effective strain

w_f = FRP width

t_f = FRP thickness

β = FRP direction

$h_{f,e}$ = effective FRP height

D_{FRP} = distribution factor

$\epsilon_{FRP,i}$ = strain in i^{th} fiber intercepted by shear crack

n = number of fibers crossed by diagonal shear crack

ϵ_{max} = maximum strain on the fiber experiencing the most strain among the other fibers intercepted by critical shear crack

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